

The interaction between callus induction and plant regeneration media is shown in Table 2. Calli produced in G1 medium could be regenerated on either M3, M5, or M7 regeneration media. Calli produced in Fj should be regener-

ated on M4, M7, or SK-11; those produced in L8 should be regenerated on M2, M3, M4, M5, or SK-11. The highest percentages of green plants were produced on M4 and M7. ■

Hybrid rice yield trials in the Mekong Delta

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We compared seven IRRI-bred rice hybrids and two check varieties in 1990 wet (WS) and dry (DS) seasons. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing, in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Yield performance of F₁ rice hybrids in Vietnam, 1990-91.

Cross	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no/panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%)
<i>1990 wet season^a</i>						
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	125	429 abc	118.6 a	28.0	7.6 a	+41.83
IR62429 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	116	396 abc	92.4 cde	26.6	6.7 b	+26.26
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	106	407 abcd	111.0 ab	28.8	6.0 bc	+16.40
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	106	473 a	97.3 bc	25.0	5.9 bcd	+13.89
IR62829 A/IR24 R	113	451 ab	80.0 bc	27.2	5.6 cd	+5.62
V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R	104	418 abc	96.0 bc	28.0	5.5 cd	+6.75
V20 A/Milyang 46 R	104	352 cd	87.6 e	30.4	5.4 cd	+4.42
MTL 58 (check)	120	369 bcd	89.0 cde	26.0	5.3 cd	
MTL 61 (check)	104	334 d	83.6 cde	22.6	5.2 d	
CV (%)		11.80	8.14			
<i>1990-91 dry season</i>						
IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	100	14	107.6	23.8	6.67	+17.02
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	99	12	99.7	21.1	5.70	+5.60
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	107	13	113.1	24.9	5.40	
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	99	13	94.7	22.5	4.87	
IR62829 A/IR24 R	99	11	86.6	22.7	3.93	
V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R	87	11	85.2	24.7	3.40	
V20 A/Milyang 46 R	89	12	82.5	27.5	3.00	
OM576 (check)	101	13	103.4	24.0	5.40	
MTL 58 (check)	105	12	95.9	24.2	5.70	
cv (%)			10.0		5.4	
LSD (0.05)			14.5		0.40	
LSD (0.01)			14.5		0.53	

^aIn a column, yields followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Yield potential

Performance of different height rice lines under intermediate deep water levels

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We evaluated 12 promising rice lines with different plant heights (semidwarf, semitall, and tall) and growth durations (90-180 d), and N level (0 and 40 kg N/ha) under intermediate deep water (up to 80 cm) during 1988. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, with rice cultivars in the main plot and N level in 15.8-m² subplots.

Experimental lines were direct seeded in dry soil 6 Jun, at 400 seeds/m² with 20-cm row spacing, and fertilized basally with 9 kg P and 17 kg K/ha. Germination was good.

Water in the field increased gradually from mid-Jun, to 76 cm on 10 Aug and 83 cm on 25 Sep. During most of the crop growth period, water level was 30-60 cm. Water receded gradually from early Oct. The crops matured in mid-Dec.

Application of N increased plant height and yield attributes significantly (see table). The four tall cultivars had significantly higher yields. They elongated faster as water level rose and flowered during the first week of Nov.

Grain yield decreased linearly with decreasing plant height, and the three semidwarfs had very low yields. Popular, short-duration upland cultivar Kalinga 3 virtually failed under deep water. Although this variety had panicle numbers similar to those of other varieties, its panicle size was considerably reduced, partly because of seed germination of matured panicles lying on the water surface and partly because of damage by birds after early maturity.

Local semitall cultivar Hathipanja had the highest 1000-grain weight but had